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Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish during the Eastern and Transitional Seasons in Pangandaran Waters, West Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Pangandaran is one of the fish landing centers in West Java, Indonesia. Migration, distribution, and abundance of pelagic fish are influenced by several oceanographic parameters such as sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-a concentration. This study was conducted to map the fishing grounds of large pelagic fish in Pangandaran Sea during the eastern and transitional seasons. Knowing the potential fishing ground in Pangandaran is very important to increase the catch of fishermen and maintain the sustainability of fisheries resources. In this study, a quantitative descriptive research method was used using a geographic information system approach. In May 2024 (transitional season 1), the average chlorophyll-a concentration ranged from 0.2 - 8 mg/m³ (mesotrophic waters) with average Sea Surface Temperature (SST) ranging from 26.13 - 29.38° C. In the eastern season (June, July, August) the average chlorophyll-a concentration was 0.2 - 2.3 mg/m³ (oligotrophic waters); 0.4 - 4.4 mg/m³ (mesotrophic waters); 11 - 33 mg/m³ (hypertrophic waters) with average sea surface temperature (SST) ranging from 28.4 - 36.5 °C; 26.6 - 32.24 °C; 23.5 - 32 °C. In September 2025 (transitional season 2), the average chlorophyll-a concentration was 1 - 18 mg/m³ (eutrophic waters), with average sea surface temperature (SST) ranging from 24.9 - 34.5 °C. The highest potential of large pelagic fish was found in June, July, and August 2024 (east season) in catch line 2. The potential catch of large pelagic fish in transitional season 1 (May 2024) was lower than in the east season, but the catch line was still in catch line 2. While in transitional season 2 (September 2024) the potential catch of large pelagic fish was lower than the east season and the catch line was outside catch line 2 (towards the open sea).

Keywords: Chlorophyll-a, fishing ground, Pangandaran, sea surface temperature, sustainability of marine fisheries resources

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesian waters are the path of the monsoon system. This is due to Indonesia's position between two large oceans and continents [1]. In a year there are two reversals of direction. In June to August there is an east monsoon, which is characterized by blowing east winds with the direction of surface currents moving from east to west, while in December to February there is a west monsoon, which is characterized by blowing west winds with the direction of surface currents moving from west to east. In March - May and September - November takes place the transitional season (transition), where in this season the movement of surface currents is irregular [2].

The distribution of chlorophyll-a in the ocean varies according to geographical location and water depth. This variation is caused by differences in sunlight intensity and nutrient concentrations contained in the waters. The distribution of chlorophyll-a concentration is higher in coastal and coastal waters, and the concentration of chlorophyll-a is low in offshore waters, but in certain areas in offshore waters there are high concentrations of chlorophyll-a. This situation is caused by the high concentration of nutrients produced through the process of lifting nutrients from the bottom layer of waters to the surface layer [3]. The concentration of chlorophyll-a in a water area has a relationship with the season [4].

The process of migration, distribution, and abundance of pelagic fish is influenced by several oceanographic parameters such as sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-a concentration [5]. Changes in the value of oceanographic parameters have been shown to affect the catch of pelagic fish in a body of water, the results of research show that pelagic fish catches tend to increase when sea surface temperatures are low and chlorophyll-a is abundant [5-7]. Changes in sea surface temperature are associated with changes in other variables, including biological variables such as chlorophyll-a, primary productivity, species physiological responses and species distribution [8-11].

Sea surface temperature is one of the main environmental oceanographic parameters that is most often needed because it is useful in studying the physical and chemical processes that occur in the ocean. Sea surface temperature is an important factor that supports the life processes and distribution of organisms in the sea and affects the metabolic activities and reproduction of marine biota [12]. Meanwhile, chlorophyll-a is a pigment capable of photosynthesis and is present in all phytoplankton organisms according to Barnes [13]. The amount of phytoplankton in marine waters can generally be seen from the amount of chlorophyll-a in it. The distribution of water fertility can be determined by mapping the distribution of chlorophyll-a concentration [14]. Analysis of the relationship between sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll-a (chl-a) improves our understanding of ocean productivity and can be used satellite imagery data to provide reliable critical information on oceanographic conditions and simultaneously support monitoring and assessment of the marine environment [7, 15].

Capture fisheries in Indonesia are still dominated by small-scale fisheries. It is estimated that there were 960,000 capture fishermen in Indonesia in 2016 [16], with about 90% of them being small-scale fishermen [17]. Capture fisheries play a crucial and strategic role in

Indonesia, as a source of economic growth, food source, and employment provider [18]. Fisheries create jobs and act as a safety net when other sources of income disappear [19]. Pangandaran is one of the fish landing centers in West Java, Indonesia. Capture fisheries is recognized as one of the major sectors that contribute to the local economy at the coastal area around Pangandaran. Pangandaran Regency falls within the WPP 573 Indian Ocean zone, covering the waters off the western tip of Sumatra and the south coast of Java [20]. The livelihood of the population in Pangandaran is mostly as fishermen which is the main income for the fishing community in Pangandaran [21]. This study was conducted to map the fishing ground areas of large pelagic fish in the Pangandaran Sea in the eastern and transitional seasons. Knowing the potential fishing ground (fishing zone) in Pangandaran is very important to increase the catch of fishermen and maintain the sustainability of fisheries resources. By knowing the location and characteristics of fishing grounds, fishermen can optimize fishing operations, reduce operational costs, and prevent overfishing.

2. METHODS

The astronomical location of Pangandaran is between longitude 108°40' E and latitude 07°43' S. The total area of Pangandaran Regency is 168,509 Ha with an area of sea of 67,340 Ha. Pangandaran Regency has a coastal length of 91 Km.

Figure 1. Research Area.

The research was conducted in Pangandaran waters in May 2024 - September 2024. In this research, the method used is quantitative descriptive research method using geographic information system approach. Spatial data obtained in the form of data satellite images

consisting of chlorophyll-a and sea surface temperature data, as well as fish catch point data and fish catch production data obtained from interviews and field observations, then these data can be visualized in the form of maps that are presented with information. Data sources for chlorophyll-a parameters and sea surface temperature parameters use Aqua MODIS level 3 images from ocean color.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Potential Fishing Ground of Pangandaran Sea

Fishing grounds are water areas where fishermen usually conduct fishing activities. This area is defined as a location where fisheries resources can be utilized sustainably and fishing gear can function optimally. The determination of fishing grounds depends not only on the presence of fish in a water area, but also on the ability of the fishing unit to operate fishing gear and conduct fishing activities in the area.

Pangandaran is one of the areas included in the WPP IX zone of the Indian Ocean which covers the waters of the western tip of the island of Sumatra and the southern coast of Java. This area is a mainstay area for marine tourism and capture fisheries. These two sectors are recorded to have contributed greatly to the regional economy and the people in the region. Capture fisheries in Pangandaran Regency are dominated by small-scale fishers.

The fishing lines used in mapping the potential fishing grounds of the Pangandaran Sea as stipulated in KKP Regulation Number 59 of 2020 concerning Fishing Lines and Fishing Tools in the State Fisheries Management Area of the Republic of Indonesia and the High Seas are Line 1A as far as 2 nautical miles, Line 1B as far as 4 nautical miles, and Line 2 as far as 12 miles.

The high intensity of fishing in coastal areas has the potential to cause over exploitation, which can threaten the sustainability of fish resources in coastal waters. Therefore, information on the distribution of fishing grounds in an area, especially in semi-enclosed and narrow waters such as bays, is very important as a basis for analyzing the impact of fishing activities in these locations and identifying the distribution of fishing points in these areas. One way to do this is by mapping potential fishing ground areas for fisheries resource management.

This mapping not only helps fishermen identify potential fishing grounds, but also allows them to identify areas with high concentrations of fish, based on the influential parameters of sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll-a concentration, which are indicators of the presence of plankton as the main food source for pelagic fish.

This mapping can also help fishermen in using vessels and fishing gear with different capacities. With a map showing fishing lanes based on regulations, such as those stipulated in KKP Regulation No.59/Permen-KP/2020, fishermen can know the permitted operating areas for their vessel types.

The article explains that fishing lanes are divided into three, namely Lane I which is used by vessels of 5 GT and is allowed to operate in coastal waters up to 12 nautical miles from the shoreline. Line II is used for vessels of 5-30 GT that are allowed to operate in waters more than 12 miles from the coastline up to a limit of 24 miles. Line III is for fishing vessels of more than 30 GT, which are allowed to operate in waters more than 24 miles from the coastline.

The number of fishing fleets (vessels) based on the same year's data is 1,958 units, most of which are catinting boats with a gross tonnage (GT) of less than 5 GT totaling 1,919 units

(98%). The boats are anchored at several points scattered along the Pangandaran coast.

There are a small number of vessels larger than 5 GT, namely 24 units of 5 - 10 GT, 4 units of 10 - 20 GT, 3 units of 20 - 30 GT and 8 units of > 30 GT. With this division of fishing lines, fishermen in Pangandaran can optimally utilize the potential of the waters without violating the rules that have been set. Fishing grounds are not solely determined by the presence of fish resources in a body of water, but are also influenced by the ability of fishing units to catch fish in the waters.

The potential fishing ground in Pangandaran Sea is also influenced by the diversity of fish species found in the waters. Based on the results of interviews conducted in two places, namely Legok Jawa and Bojong Salawe, the majority of the catches are large pelagic fish species. The catches in Legok Jawa include lobster, tuna, layur (the main catch that produces 4-5 quintals), and kebu.

While for the catch in Bojong Salawe, the dominating fish for the last 5 months are white pomfret, layur, mackerel, kerong-kerong, three faces with a seasonal yield of 2-3 quintals. Fishermen in this area use a variety of fishing methods, such as pursein nets, gill nets, and fishing rods. This combination of fishing gear allows fishermen to catch various types of fish from various water zones, both on the sea surface and seabed.

The potential of the fishing ground is enormous and is supported by oceanographic factors, fish species diversity, supporting ecosystems, and fishing technology used by local fishers. However, the sustainability of this potential is highly dependent on good management, including efforts to prevent overfishing and maintain the health of marine ecosystems.

3. 2. Potential Fishing Ground for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in May 2024

The map of potential fishing grounds for large pelagic fish in Pangandaran Sea in May 2024 shows several areas with varying fishing potential. High potential zones for large pelagic fishing (layur or mackerel) are marked in red. On this map, it can be seen that the high potential areas are concentrated at several points in the offshore waters. These zones are surrounded by yellow (medium potential) and green (low potential) areas, showing the different fishing potentials in each area.

High potential areas are marked with red circles around waters with higher chlorophyll-a concentrations. This indicates the presence of abundant food resources in the area, which tend to attract large pelagic fish species such as tuna or skipjack.

The highest chlorophyll-a concentrations were found around the coast or in catch line 1A, ranging from 0.4 - 8 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentrations in catch line 1B were 0.2 - 5.8 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in catch line 2 (offshore waters), 0.6 - 2.6 mg/m³. The fertility classification based on chlorophyll-a concentration, is included in mesotrophic waters, which means the waters have a moderate level of fertility.

In addition, Sea Surface Temperature (SST) ranging from 26.13 °C to 29.38 °C also affects fish distribution, with large pelagic fish more likely to be found in warmer waters. This map displays three catch lines (Line 1A, 1B, and Line 2) showing potential routes that fishing vessels can follow to reach fishing grounds with higher chances of catch.

This map provides useful guidance for fishermen in determining strategic areas for large pelagic fishing during May 2024.

Figure 2. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in May 2024

3. 3. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in June 2024

The main factor affecting this potential distribution is the chlorophyll-a concentration (mg/m³), which is represented by the contour lines on the map. Areas with higher chlorophyll-a concentrations tend to attract more large pelagic fish due to the presence of abundant plankton, their main food source.

The highest chlorophyll-a concentrations were found around the coast or in catch line 1A, valued at 0.8 - 2.3 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in catch line 1B, 0.8 - 1.6 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in capture line 2 (offshore waters), 0.2 - 1 mg/m³. The fertility classification based on chlorophyll-a concentration is oligotrophic, which means that the waters have low chlorophyll-a content, indicating little phytoplankton (algae) growth and limited nutrients.

In addition, sea surface temperature (SST) also affects the distribution of fish. In this map, the temperature varies between 28.416 °C to 36.5 °C, with warmer areas tending to have higher fishing potential. The map also shows fishing lanes differentiated into Lanes 1A, 1B, and 2.

These lanes provide clues on the routes fishers can take to maximize their catch in areas with higher potential. With this information, fishermen are expected to be more effective in determining the location and route of large pelagic fishing during June 2024.

Figure 3. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in June 2024.

3. 4. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in July 2024

The highest chlorophyll-a concentration was found around the coast or in catch line 1A, valued at 1.8 - 4.4 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in catch line 1B, is 1.8 - 3.9 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in capture line 2 (offshore waters), was 0.4 - 2.5 mg/m³. The fertility classification based on chlorophyll-a concentration, is included in mesotrophic waters, which means the waters have a moderate level of fertility.

In addition, sea surface temperature (SST) in July varied between 26.575 °C and 32.24 °C, with lower temperatures generally associated with areas of higher fishing potential. This supports the activities of fishermen catching pelagic fish, as these species prefer cooler temperatures.

The fishing lines shown in the map, such as Line 1A, 1B and Line 2, follow the distribution of fishing potential, allowing fishers to reach the most productive areas. In July, small- to medium-scale fishers in Pangandaran can take advantage of this increase in ocean productivity more efficiently, especially since the high potential zones are located relatively close to their fishing lines.

Figure 4. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in July 2024.

3. 5. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in August 2024

Based on the map of potential fishing grounds in August 2024, it shows three main zones that indicate the level of fishing potential, which are divided into:

- **Low Potential Zone (green color):** Areas with low potential are scattered around the coast of Pangandaran and most of the waters in the east and south. In these areas, the availability of large pelagic fish is relatively low.
- **Medium Potential Zone (yellow color):** Medium potential zones are seen around the southern coast and offshore areas.
- **High Potential Zone (red color):** This zone is located in the deeper offshore sections, indicating that the area is the best fishing ground for large pelagic fish in this period. Fishermen operating in this area have the potential to catch more.

The highest chlorophyll-a concentrations were found around the coast or in catch line 1A, ranging from 11 - 33 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentrations in catch line 1B, valued at 8 - 18 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in catch line 2 (offshore waters), is 1 - 12 mg/m³.

Fertility classifications based on chlorophyll-a concentrations include eutrophic (catchment lines 1B and 2) and hypertrophic (coastal areas or catchment line 1A) waters.

Hypertrophic waters describe water conditions that are very rich in nutrients (eutrophic) with very rapid and excessive phytoplankton growth, while eutrophic waters describe water conditions that are rich in nutrients, especially nitrogen and phosphorus, which support excessive phytoplankton growth. Eutrophic and hypertrophic conditions can cause environmental problems such as algal blooms, water quality degradation, and disruption of aquatic ecosystems. Sea Surface Temperature (SST) shows a temperature range from 23.54 °C to 32 °C. Lower temperatures are more favorable for large pelagic fish like tuna, as they tend to stay in cooler waters.

This map shows several fishing lines, identified as Line 1A, 1B, and Line 2. Line 1A passes through medium and high potential areas, which may be the fishing line used by fishers to access catch areas with higher potential for large pelagic fish. Whereas Line 1B and Line 2 also pass through areas of medium to high potential, indicating they are important routes for small to medium-sized fishing vessels to fish in more productive zones.

Figure 5. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in August 2024

3. 6. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in September 2024

Chlorophyll-a concentration around the coast or in catch line 1A, is 5 - 15 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in fishing line 1B, is 5 - 18 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a concentration in

catch line 2, value 1 - 13 mg/m³. The fertility classification based on chlorophyll-a concentration is included in eutrophic waters. Eutrophic waters describe water conditions that are rich in nutrients, especially nitrogen and phosphorus, which support excessive phytoplankton growth. In eutrophic waters, rapid phytoplankton growth results in high chlorophyll-a concentrations. Eutrophic conditions can lead to various environmental problems, such as algal blooms, water quality degradation, and disruption of aquatic ecosystems.

Recorded sea surface temperatures (SST) ranging from 24.87 °C to 34.54 °C play an important role in supporting the distribution of large pelagic fish in the area, where areas with optimal temperatures usually support the presence of fish. Overall, this map provides an important guide for fishermen to maximize their catch by focusing on high potential areas, while still paying attention to the sustainable management of fisheries resources in Pangandaran Sea.

Figure 6. Potential Fishing Grounds for Large Pelagic Fish in Pangandaran Sea in September 2024

The annual distribution of chlorophyll-a concentration has an inverse pattern with sea surface temperature, where chlorophyll-a concentration tends to increase when sea surface temperature values decrease. The monthly fluctuation pattern of chlorophyll-a concentration values tends to increase during the east season (June, July, August) and transitional season 2 (September, October, November) compared to the west season (December, January, February) and transitional season 1 (March, April, May).

Chlorophyll-a concentrations in the western season tend to be lower than in the eastern season [22, 23]. This is due to the Southeast Monsoon, which causes chlorophyll-a concentrations to increase in the South. Another cause is the presence of the South Equatorial Current (SEC) in the eastern season will push the water mass in the southern waters of Java to the west, causing a void in the water mass and requiring upwelling to fill the void [24]. The low SST in the eastern season is due to the position of the sun in the northern part of the earth so that areas in the south get less sunlight. The variation of Ekman transport on the south coast of Java during the eastern monsoon moving towards the open sea corresponds to the high concentration of chlorophyll-a [25]. Seasonal winds can also influence Ekman transport called wind-driven Ekman flow, which can move water masses and nutrients within them [26] for example through upwelling and downwelling phenomena.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) In May 2024 (transitional season 1), average chlorophyll-a concentrations ranged from 0.2 - 8 mg/m³ (mesotrophic waters) with average Sea Surface temperatures (SST) ranging from 26.13 - 29.38 °C. In June 2024 (eastern season) the average chlorophyll-a concentration was 0.2 - 2.3 mg/m³ (oligotrophic waters), with an average sea surface temperature (SST) ranging from 28.4 - 36.5 °C. In July 2024 (east monsoon) the average chlorophyll-a concentration was 0.4 - 4.4 mg/m³ (mesotrophic waters) with average sea surface temperatures (SST) ranging from 26.6 - 32.24 °C. In August (east monsoon) the average chlorophyll-a concentration was 11 - 33 mg/m³ (hypertrophic waters) and 1 - 18 mg/m³ (eutrophic waters) (catchment lines 1B and 2) and hypertrophic (coastal areas or catchment line 1A). Mean Sea Surface temperature (SST) ranges from 23.5 - 32 °C. In September 2025 (transitional season 2), the average chlorophyll-a concentration was 1 - 18 mg/m³ (eutrophic waters), with average sea surface temperature (SST) ranging from 24.9 - 34.5 °C.
- 2) The highest potential of large pelagic fish was found in June, July, and August 2024 (east season) in catch line 2. The potential catch of large pelagic fish in transitional season 1 (May 2024) was lower than in the east season, but the catch line was still in catch line 2. Whereas in transitional season 2 (September 2024) the potential catch of large pelagic fish was lower than the east season and the catch line was outside catch line 2 (towards the open sea).

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